

D1.4 Project Management Plan – Month 2

Date : 24.07.2024

Deliverable No : D1.4

Responsible Partner : CIRCE

Dissemination Level : PU

Short Description	
The WILSON Project Management Plan (Deliverable 1.4) guides the consortium members through the project's structure and phases, detailing team roles, WP objectives, Gantt charts, progress checkpoints, and interactions. It complements the Grant and Consortium Agreements. Updated periodically, it ensures alignment, minimizes conflicts, and optimizes resource use, supporting successful project execution and sustainable building management.	

Project Information	
Project Acronym:	WILSON
Project Title:	Distributed data modelling and Federated Digital Twinning for lifecycle data-driven sustainable operation and management of buildings and districts
Project Coordinator:	CIRCE
Duration:	48 months

Document Information & Version Management			
Document Title:		D1.4 Project Management Plan – Month 2	
Related WP/Task:		WPI / T1.1	
Document Type:		Report	
Main Author(s):		CIRCE (Aleida Lostale)	
Contributor(s):		Project Consortium	
Reviewed by:		Project Consortium	
Approved by:		CIRCE (Aleida Lostale)	
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
V1.0	28.06.2024	CIRCE (Aleida Lostale)	
V1.1	24.07.2024	Project consortium	

Disclaimer	
Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2.	INTRODUCTION	8
3.	TEAM COMPOSITION AND ROLES PER ENTITY	9
4.	WORK PACKAGES INTERACTION.....	12
5.	WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE.....	14
5.1.	WPI-2-3 Management and coordination.....	14
5.1.1.	WPI-2-3 Objectives	14
5.1.2.	WPI-2-3 Gantt Chart.....	14
5.1.3.	WPI-2-3 Deliverables.....	14
5.1.4.	WPI-2-3 Milestones	15
5.2.	WP4 Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios	15
5.2.1.	WP4 Objectives.....	15
5.2.2.	WP4 Gantt Chart	15
5.2.3.	WP4 Deliverables	15
5.2.4.	WP4 Milestones.....	16
5.3.	WP5-6 Semantic and federated digital twins at local and district levels	17
5.3.1.	WP5-6 Objectives.....	17
5.3.2.	WP5-6 Gantt Chart.....	17
5.3.3.	WP5-6 Deliverables.....	17
5.3.4.	WP5-6 Milestones.....	18
5.4.	WP7-8 Data interoperability for data mesh enabled digital twins	19
5.4.1.	WP7-8 Objectives	19
5.4.2.	WP7-8 Gantt Chart.....	19
5.4.3.	WP7-8 Deliverables	19
5.4.4.	WP7-8 Milestones	20
5.5.	WP9-10 Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses.....	20
5.5.1.	WP9-10 Objectives	20
5.5.2.	WP9-10 Gantt Chart.....	20
5.5.3.	WP9-10 Deliverables.....	21
5.5.4.	WP9-10 Milestones	21
5.6.	WPII-12 Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for non - energy uses	22
5.6.1.	WPII-12 Objectives.....	22
5.6.2.	WPII-12 Gantt Chart.....	22

5.6.3.	WP11-12 Deliverables	23
5.6.4.	WP11-12 Milestones	23
5.7.	WP13 Integration of technologies and preparation for large-scale pilots	24
5.7.1.	WP13 Objectives	24
5.7.2.	WP13 Gantt Chart.....	24
5.7.3.	WP13 Deliverables.....	24
5.7.1.	WP13 Milestones	25
5.8.	WP14 Large-scale demonstration campaign.....	26
5.8.1.	WP14 Objectives	26
5.8.2.	WP14 Gantt Chart.....	26
5.8.3.	WP14 Deliverables.....	26
5.8.4.	WP14 Milestones.....	26
5.9.	WP15 Impacts and guarantees of replication	27
5.9.1.	WP15 Objectives	27
5.9.2.	WP15 Gantt Chart.....	27
5.9.3.	WP15 Tasks	27
5.9.4.	WP15 Milestones.....	28
5.10.	WP16-17-18 Dissemination, communication and exploitation.....	29
5.10.1.	WP16-17-18 Objectives.....	29
5.10.2.	WP16-17-18 Gantt Chart	29
5.10.1.	WP16-17-18 Tasks.....	29
5.10.2.	WP16-17-18 Milestones.....	30
6.	RISK ASSESSMENT.....	32
7.	CONCLUSIONS	36

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 WILSON Pert Chart	13
Figure 2 WP1-2-3 Gantt Chart.....	14
Figure 4 WP4 Gantt Chart	15
Figure 5 WP5-6 Gantt Chart	17
Figure 6 WP7-8 Gantt Chart.....	19
Figure 7 WP9-10 Gantt Chart	21
Figure 8 WP11-12 Gantt Chart.....	22
Figure 9 WP13 Gantt Chart.....	24
Figure 10 WP14 Gantt Chart.....	26
Figure 11 WP15 Gantt Chart.....	27
Figure 12 WP16-17-18 Gantt Chart.....	29

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Team composition and roles per entity	9
Table 2 WP1-2-3 Deliverables	14
Table 3 WP1-2-3 Milestones	15
Table 4 WP4 Deliverables.....	16
Table 5 WP4 Milestones.....	17
Table 6 WP5-6 Deliverables.....	17
Table 7 WP5-6 Milestones	18
Table 8 WP7-8 Deliverables	19
Table 9 WP7-8 Milestones	20
Table 10 WP9-10 Deliverables.....	21
Table 11 WP9-10 Milestones	21
Table 12 WP11-12 Deliverables	23
Table 13 WP11-12 Milestones	24
Table 14 WP13 Deliverables.....	24
Table 15 WP13 Milestones.....	25
Table 16 WP14 Deliverables	26
Table 17 WP14 Milestones.....	27
Table 18 WP15 Deliverables	28
Table 19 WP15 Milestones.....	28
Table 20 WP16-17-18 Deliverables.....	29
Table 21 WP16-17-18 Milestones	30
Table 22 WILSON Critical Risks.....	32

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
DBL	Digital Building Logbook
DT	Digital Twin
EoL	End of Life
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
IDS	International Data Space
IDS	Information Delivery Specification
INN	Innovation
IoT	Internet of Things
KG	Knowledge Graph
LBD	Linked Building Data
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PDHs	Personalised Data Hubs
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PMP	Project Management Plan
QMP	Quality Management Plan
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SLA	Service level agreement
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
UC	Use Case
UHI	Urban Heat Island
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 1.4 contains the first version of WILSON Project Management Plan. This report aims to act as a guidance for the 16 consortium members of WILSON to understand the project structure and implementation phases of every Work Package (WP). Relevant contents such as team composition and capabilities, specific objectives and expectations, Gantt Chart, checkpoints for controlling work progress and interactions between WPs, are detailed.

This deliverable complements the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement of WILSON project and will be used in conjunction with them.

2. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 1.4 Project Management Plan (PMP) is the first version of the document that aims to align all partners of WILSON project towards the same goals. Global specifications of the project, objectives as well as the interdependencies between work packages and tasks are defined and put together within a well-organized structure. Objectives are clearly defined and checkpoints for controlling work progress are determined.

As a summary, D1.4 is a comprehensive guide of WILSON project which aims to minimize misunderstandings, conflicts, and use of resources. Based on this document, each partner will further develop its methods or strategies to be used during project implementation.

The present Project Management Plan will evolve as the project progresses. At any time, the PMP will reflect the current state of the consortium's agreements regarding time schedule per task and subtask, responsible partners, dependencies on other tasks and results.

The PMP will be updated three additional times during the project execution in M18, M36 and M48 according to the Annex I of the Grant Agreement no. 101147267.

3. TEAM COMPOSITION AND ROLES PER ENTITY

The present section introduces the different entities that participates in WILSON project, their members and which is the role they are going to perform during the lifetime of the project. The name of the employees has been obtained from the contact list of the project.

Table 1 Team composition and roles per entity

Entity and participants	Role in the project
1/ CIRCE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aleida Lostale • Andreas Muñoz • Aitor Alcrudo • Rafael Camarero • Pablo Inda • Francisco Gómez 	Project coordinator. Developer of P2P services framework (INN3) and analytics & energy management toolset (INN4); WP9-10 and WP13 leader (integration of WILSON technologies and living lab); support in all energy solutions, given their extensive experience in this field; leader of T4.1, T7.2/T8.2, T7.4/T8.4.
2/ CSTB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nicoleta Schiopu • Bruno Fies • Nicolas Pastorelly • Aline Brachet • Emilie Gully • Mathieu Quenard • Georgios Kyriakodis • Edouard Sorin • Marine Vesson • Stéphanie Derouineau • Isabelle Bachelier • Laurent Suteau 	Developer of HIBOU (biodiversity, INN6) and LOD LIFTER (circularity, INN7). Leader of T9.4 and WP11-12.
3/ TUE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pieter Pauwels • Ekaterina Petrova • Ravi Sharma • Avinash Ramachandrani 	Developer of PDHs (INN2), leader of WP7-8, ontologies definition (T5.2/T6.2), interface for Asset Management Systems, BMS and Digital Logbook (T9.1/T10.1).
4/ RINA-C <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serena SCOTTON • Monia DI NUCCI • Enrica GROSSO • Carlos Daniel Huertas • Alberto MARASI • Arianna Verga • Ayme Ballagas 	Developer of Risk and resilience tool (INN8); leader of WP14, KPIs definition (T4.5), LCA/LCC of BMS (T11.4/T12.4), deployment & monitoring plan (T13.1), holistic impact assessment and CBA (T15.1), and Italian pilot.

Entity and participants	Role in the project
5/ QUE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christos Tsalis 	Developer of BIM-enabled SRIs calculator (INN9), WP4 leader. Overall technical and development support.
6/ PARQ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abraham Jiménez Carla Romagosa Maria Garcia Raul Garcia 	Supporting on BIM and DTs development as well as Spanish pilot.
7/ WATTX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simon Müller Sewin Tariverdian Christian Schwöbel 	Technology manufacturer. Data provision mainly for Swiss pilot.
8/ ADD <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Piero Pelizzaro Valentina Flaminio Vittoria Mobili Fabio Garagozzo 	Public owner of the Italian large-scale pilot and data provision for WILSON UCs demonstration.
9/ HMRIB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carol Barnwell Marina Sirvent Aina Bernal 	Leader of the Spanish demo site. Owner of the Spanish large-scale pilot and data provision for WILSON UCs demonstration.
10/ IDSA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silvia Castellvi Sonia Jimenez Rahmi Akinci 	Reference entity in data sovereignty, global standards for IDS and connectors. Extensive contacts network and synergies with existing projects and initiatives. Leader of T15.4 (standards and policy).
11/ GND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donatas Ditikus Gabija Stanislovaityte 	Developer of the Investment Planning Tool (KER10), overall management activities and technical tasks support. Leader of WP15.
11.1/ GND.A <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donatas Ditikus Gabija Stanislovaityte 	Overall financial (advisory), sustainability and business support.
12/ INTRACT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kubra Yurduseven Nilay Yoruk Dilan Bingol 	Leader of WP16-17-18. Responsible for communication, exploitation & dissemination strategy and actions.
13/ HSLU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christoph Imboden Andreas Rumsch Eugen Rodel 	Leader of Data Space architecture definition and infrastructure setup (T5.1) and technical support in related tasks;

Entity and participants	Role in the project
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edith Birrer • Martin Friedli • Stefan Winterberger • Joëlle Clot • Jekaterina Dmitrijeva • Marco Kunz • Shaun West 	large-scale demonstration set-up (T13.4) and Swiss pilot.
14/ SAK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Florian Stemplinger 	Owner of the Swiss pilot and data provision for WILSON UCs demonstration.
15/ UNEW <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mohamad Kassem • Xiang Xie • Philip James • Deborah Grieves 	Developer of federated DT (INNI) at local and district level and CIMBA tool (INN5). Leader of WP5-6; analysis of business cases and main pilots' requirements (T4.2).
16/ BAM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • John Seager 	Leader of the UK demo site. Private owner of the UK demo-site and data provision for WILSON UCs demonstration.

4. WORK PACKAGES INTERACTION

All project activities will be supported during the project execution by a coherent and smooth management and coordination articulated under **WP1, WP2 and WP3**. These WPs will provide the necessary tools, methods and governing structure for effective and comprehensive administrative, financial, technical and legal management to ensure the successful project execution. The core project work starts in **WP4**, in which an exhaustive analysis of boundary conditions needed for the correct development of the solutions in the pilots (Italy, Spain, UK and Switzerland) will be carried out, setting the technical and technological requirements for the subsequent development of WILSON solutions. In parallel, an identification and analysis of the business cases will be performed in this WP to identify end users needs and requirements, and the definition of the KPIs and data handling main requirements will be carried out.

Once all reference conditions and information are established, design and development of the technologies to be implemented at the demonstrators will be performed in parallel during WP5 to WP12. **WP5-WP6** will focus on the definition of data space architecture and its components, the ontologies, as well as on the development of the digital twins at local and district level. **WP7-8** will focus on the design and development of the Personalised Data Hubs and corresponding data interaction mechanisms (blockchain access control, IDS connectors, APIs). On the other hand, **WP9-WP10** will be dedicated to the innovations regarding energy uses, while **WP11-12** will focus on non-energy uses.

WP13 will deal with the planning of the demonstration, the integration of technologies and solutions developed in previous WPs, and their implementation and validation at TRL6 in the Spanish living lab. Finally, this WP will prepare the large-scale pilots for the real demonstration of the solutions in the following WP. Once these tasks are finished, **WP14** will push the WILSON solutions to TRL7-8 through the demonstration across the four large-scale pilots, which will conclude with a task dedicated to the compilation of results, cost-benefit analysis and KPIs evaluation across the four large scale demo sites.

In parallel to the demonstration of WILSON solutions, business modelling, investment tools and plans will be developed in **WP15** to study their impact and replication potential, resulting in the development of new finance models, market opportunities and policy recommendations that will foster the further uptake of WILSON solutions.

Finally, a coherent dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy will be defined and implemented from the very beginning of the project in **WP16, WP17 and WP18**. These WPs will assure the correct transfer of WILSON results to the target stakeholders and will establish synergies with other on-going projects and initiatives, including the exploitation and IPR management of the project developments.

Figure 1 WILSON Pert Chart

Table 4 WP4 Deliverables

D4.1 Detailed models of buildings at demonstration pilots	CIRCE	R, SEN	M10
The document will provide detailed information of the pilots, including the present architecture and equipment, but also the requirements by solutions developers for the next steps of the project.			
D4.2 WILSON use and business cases definition	UNEW	R, PU	M10
Capture the business use cases for WILSON developments from a diverse stakeholder group using a combination of a comprehensive literature review, questionnaire and focus groups in order to gather user requirements, and define key factors (challenges, preferences, expectations) affecting the development of Wilson technical solutions and its uptakes. Successful completion of T4.2 will inform the subsequent WPs for data interoperability, energy and non-energy services.			
D4.3 BIM-to-SRI methodology and tool	QUE	OTHER, SEN	M10
This deliverable describes the functionalities of the BIM-to-SRI methodology and tool, presenting an automated workflow for precise calculation of the SRI score based on BIM data collected through the WILSON data mesh approach. Emphasising compliance with the IDS (Information Delivery Specification) and MVD (Model View Definition) standards, it also reports on the data models developed to semantically represent the I/O requirement of the tool.			
D4.4 Data handling, management and protection	QUE	R, SEN	M10
Detailed documentation of the data made available and used in the project, together with characteristics and the requirements for their effective, performant, and secure management and sharing according to FAIR principles. Assessment and guidelines of practices for protection of personal data and cybersecurity measures will be included.			
D4.5 WILSON KPIs life-cycle oriented indicators panel	RINA-C	R, PU	M10
Panel of KPIs to evaluate the innovation and effectiveness of WILSON solutions. The KPIs will be used for overall assessment of pilots, mainly aiming at benchmarking their performance, in meeting the SDGs. Sources of information for KPIs definition are obtained from the analysis of the impacts from the data management, operation, sustainability and resilience perspectives, among others, aiming to be as aligned as possible with Built4People. These KPIs will be also identified to benchmark WILSON technologies and services with competitor technologies and current demo-sites situations. The KPIs panel will represent a draft of the monitoring and assessment plan to be put in place early in WILSON pilots to guarantee that the necessary sensors and building assets are working properly. The foreseen sensors typically include energy (distributed energy generation, electrical power production, demand and storage meters, etc.), and non-energy (environmental performance, circularity, building systems) monitoring systems.			

5.2.4. WP4 Milestones

Table 5 presents the milestones related to WP4 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

D5.2-6.1 WILSON ontologies evaluation	TUE	R, PU	M18, M30
Reports that present the ontologies that are developed, using UML and ontology engineering methods, in support of the WILSON data architecture (T5.1, T7.1). These ontologies are to be adopted in the implementation of local and/or district DT in WILSON. The report includes full documentation, and direct links to properly published ontologies.			
D5.3-6.2 Local and Federated district-level Digital Twins	UNEW	R, PU	M18, M30
Reports including the work to create the Local Digital Twins (at per building/dwelling level) and the Federated Digital Twins (at district level) that can be tested in the WILSON living labs and large-scale pilots. The creation of Local DT will use building information and enable testing of building response to different scenarios (e.g., weather conditions, occupancy levels). The creation of Federated DT will connect local DTs with district level infrastructures and other urban parameters based on data mesh principles.			
D5.3-6.2 Local and Federated district-level Digital Twins	UNEW	R, PU	M18, M30
Reports including the work to create the Local Digital Twins (at per building/dwelling level) and the Federated Digital Twins (at district level) that can be tested in the WILSON living labs and large-scale pilots. The creation of Local DT will use building information and enable testing of building response to different scenarios (e.g., weather conditions, occupancy levels). The creation of Federated DT will connect local DTs with district level infrastructures and other urban parameters based on data mesh principles.			

5.3.4. WP5-6 Milestones

Table 7 presents the milestones related to WP5-6 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Table 7 WP5-6 Milestones

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
4	Data spaces fully defined. Solutions developments' alpha version available Exploitation activities ready to start	TUE	M19	WP5, WP7, WP9 and WP11 checked and accepted. Architectures, models and algorithms initially developed and have been validated in a closed environment. Start of T17.2.
6	WILSON decentralised data mesh, software modules and suite of tools ready	UNEW	M31	WP6, WP8, WP10 and WP12 DLVs checked and accepted. Project tools and models are completed with full functionalities and ready to test. First tests of the solutions conducted in the Spanish living lab.
10	End of WILSON project	CIRCE	M48	All deliverables checked and approved WP leaders and the PC.

D7.4-8.4 API software for data ingestion and system integration	CIRCE	OTHER, PU	M18, M30
1 st and final version of explanation of the data and system integration methods developed along the project to interconnect the heterogeneous systems of the pilots.			

5.4.4. WP7-8 Milestones

Table 9 presents the milestones related to WP7-8 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Table 9 WP7-8 Milestones

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
4	Data spaces fully defined. Solutions developments' alpha version available Exploitation activities ready to start	TUE	M19	WP5, WP7, WP9 and WP11 checked and accepted. Architectures, models and algorithms initially developed and have been validated in a closed environment. Start of T17.2.
6	WILSON decentralised data mesh, software modules and suite of tools ready	UNEW	M31	WP6, WP8, WP10 and WP12 DLVs checked and accepted. Project tools and models are completed with full functionalities and ready to test. First tests of the solutions conducted in the Spanish living lab.
10	End of WILSON project	CIRCE	M48	All deliverables checked and approved WP leaders and the PC.

5.5. WP9-10 Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses

5.5.1. WP9-10 Objectives

To develop a set of data-driven solutions to maximise interoperability of assets, data sharing and optimise their operation focusing on energy aspects. This also includes the development of a secure blockchain-based framework that will allow the deployment of WILSON's data governance solutions and innovative business models. This work will start in WP9 and continue and finalise in WP10 that will end up with the final versions of the solutions and modules for energy uses, being able to fully integrate and demonstrate their operation and interoperability in WP13.

5.5.2. WP9-10 Gantt Chart

WP9 starts at month 10 and finishes at M18 and WP10 starts at month 19 and finishes at M30. Both of them are led by CIRCE.

5.6.3. WP11-12 Deliverables

WP11-12 are comprised of the following deliverables.

Table 12 WP11-12 Deliverables

D11.1-12.1 CIMBA: predictive maintenance tool	UNEW	OTHER, SEN	M18, M30
1 st and final version of CIMBA development, a predictive maintenance tool, that utilises transfer learning techniques to train asset degradation models using homogenous asset data from building portfolios. The CIMBA tool in T11.1 and T12.1 will be verified by assessing its capabilities to predict remaining useful life, create adaptive maintenance schedules, and adjust degradation patterns based on selected variables (e.g. climatic hazard projections) hence, helping to mitigate failure risks and downtime.			
D11.2-12.2 Methodology for climate & biodiversity impacts	CSTB	R, PU	M18, M30
1 st and final version of reports on the biodiversity and climate KPI calculation method. The reports will give detailed information about the method used for the calculation of the KPI specific to the climate change and the biodiversity impacts. For the biodiversity, both in-situ (local) and ex-situ (global) impacts will be assessed. The nexus between the two types of impacts will be considered through the end point Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach.			
D11.3-12.3 Risk and vulnerability & LCA/LCC integration	CSTB	R, PU	M18, M30
D11.3 and D12.3 will describe the work carried out in Task 11.3 and 11.4 (and 12.3 and 12.4), specifically related to risk and vulnerability assessment (Task 11.3/12.3) and LCA and LCC (Task 11.4/12.4). Specifically, for what concern the Task 11.3 (12.3) it will describe (in terms of guidelines supported by evidence-based analysis) how the risk and resilience assessment support the decision-making process in the management and performance assessment of buildings, integrating the outcomes from resilience-based analysis for current and future scenarios in terms of climatic impacts to buildings. On the other hand, it will provide guidelines on how to Integrate LCA and LCC into BMS.			
D11.3-12.3 Risk and vulnerability & LCA/LCC integration	CSTB	R, PU	M18, M30
D11.3 and D12.3 will describe the work carried out in Task 11.3 and 11.4 (and 12.3 and 12.4), specifically related to risk and vulnerability assessment (Task 11.3/12.3) and LCA and LCC (Task 11.4/12.4). Specifically, for what concern the Task 11.3 (12.3) it will describe (in terms of guidelines supported by evidence-based analysis) how the risk and resilience assessment support the decision-making process in the management and performance assessment of buildings, integrating the outcomes from resilience-based analysis for current and future scenarios in terms of climatic impacts to buildings. On the other hand, it will provide guidelines on how to Integrate LCA and LCC into BMS.			

5.6.4. WP11-12 Milestones

Table 13 presents the milestones related to WP11-12 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Report showcasing the tests performed on the different technologies in the Spanish living lab, and the results obtained from the integration of these technologies.			
D13.3 Integration of WILSON technologies in living lab	CIRCE	R, SEN	M41
Report showcasing the tests performed on the different technologies in the Spanish living lab, and the results obtained from the integration of these technologies.			
D13.2 Pilots commissioning and TRL8 preparation	HSLU	R, PU	M36
Each WILSON pilot will require a technological set up and integration, carried out in premises of the technical partners of the project, to enable the large-scale demonstration. The deliverable thus will be a detailed summary of work performed in the 4 pilots regarding the installation of any assets or works required for the demonstration campaign.			

5.7.1. WPI3 Milestones

Table 5 presents the milestones related to WPI3 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Table 15 WPI3 Milestones

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
6	WILSON decentralised data mesh, software modules and suite of tools ready	UNEW	M31	WP6, WP8, WP10 and WP12 DLVs checked and accepted. Project tools and models are completed with full functionalities and ready to test. First tests of the solutions conducted in the Spanish living lab.
7	Integration of technologies completed. Installation and commissioning finalised and start of large-scale demonstration	CIRCE	M36	Integration completed (T13.2 finalised) and first 6 months of WILSON living lab test completed. Pilots' equipment installation ready (D13.2 checked and approved). Start of large-scale demonstration campaign (WP14).
8	Tools refined after living lab completion. Reach of half of large-scale demonstration.	HSLU	M41	KPIs checked and modifications of tools carried out with feedback gathered. WPI3 DLV checked and approved.
10	End of WILSON project	CIRCE	M48	All deliverables checked and approved WP leaders and the PC.

Table 18 WP15 Deliverables

D15.1 Evaluation of key results, impact assessment and CBA	RINA-C	R, PU	M48
<p>D15.1 will contain the analysis and evaluation of WILSON based on the Impact Assessment methodology defined in T4.5. It will focus on aspects such as: i) professionals' overall interest and acceptance regarding the proposed services, ii) technical/functional performance and the comparison of results, iii) evaluation of costs-benefits and feasibility of proposed services, iv) problems met and solved, v) recommendations for improvement and suggested extensions. The KPIs (T4.5 and T13.1) will be measured at the beginning and end of the demonstration campaign by pilot coordinators to assess impacts achieved. Based on the KPI results, the deliverable will gather the lessons learnt and provide the economic and social impacts of the most promising results based on the calculation of Cost/Benefit Ratios (CBR).</p>			
D15.2 Investment planning tool and new business models	GND	OTHER, PU	M48
<p>The specification of the Investment Tool providing stakeholders with in-depth insights to support their decision-making processes on operation, renovation and installation of green, sustainable assets. The Investment tool will be based on the expertise of GND focused on the environmental-financial data collections from sustainable energy and energy efficiency related projects and its visualization to investors. The investment tool will be integrated into GND infrastructure (www.gnd.one) as a GND asset increasing outreach of the WILSON project. The investment tool will support investors' decision-making process and integrate technical factors (such as energy efficiency improvements, reduced operational costs, etc.) with economical ones (such as increased property value, associated upfront expenses), providing stakeholders with comprehensive insights aiding their decision-making processes regarding operation and planned investments. The investment tool will support the development of new business models. The tool will cater to a vast audience of sustainable energy investors, boosting the project's reach even post-completion.</p>			
D15.3 Standardisation and policy recommendations	IDSA	R, PU	M48
<p>Comprehensive report on the main regulations and standards related to WILSON solutions and Data Spaces. Furthermore, the deliverable will report the conclusions of the workshops organized to consolidate industry recommendations to EU and national legislators, as well as the recommendations identified within the project for relevant standardization communities or for the creation of new standards.</p>			

5.9.4. WP15 Milestones

Table 5 presents the milestones related to WP15 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Table 19 WP15 Milestones

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
5	WILSON solutions start integration planning and preparation for	INTRACT	M25	Pilot partners start concrete conversations with developers for implementation (WP13 starts).

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
	large-scale demonstration. Initial exploitation routes designed.			Initial agreements reached on exploitation routes for developed innovation (D17.4 checked and approved).
10	End of WILSON project	CIRCE	M48	All deliverables checked and approved WP leaders and the PC.

5.10. WP16–17–18 Dissemination, communication and exploitation

5.10.1. WP16–17–18 Objectives

To define and implement dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities to be carried out throughout (and after) the project to ensure WILSON results will effectively benefit built environment data management and reach the market. Contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions.

5.10.2. WP16–17–18 Gantt Chart

WP16 starts at month 1 and finishes at M18, WP17 starts at month 19 and finishes at M36 and WP18 starts at month 37 and finishes at the end of the project (month 48). All of them are led by INTRACT.

[2023-CL5-D4-02-01] WILSON Gantt chart		Total duration (months)	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
			M1	M4	M8	M12	M13	M16	M20	M24	M25	M28	M32	M36	M37	M40	M44	M48
WP16-WP17-WP18	INTRACT Dissemination, communication and exploitation		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T16.1-T17.1-T18.1	INTRACT Communication and dissemination strategy and actions	48	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T16.2-T17.2-T18.2	INTRACT Networking and synergies with former and on-going projects and initiatives	48	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T17.3-T18.3	INTRACT Identification of final key exploitable results and IPR assessment	48	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

Figure 11 WP16–17–18 Gantt Chart

5.10.1. WP16–17–18 Tasks

WP16–17–18 are comprised of the following deliverables.

Table 20 WP16–17–18 Deliverables

D16.1–16.2–17.1–18.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan & Execution Report	INTRACT	R, PU	M4, M18, M36, M48
The report serves as a dynamic and comprehensive framework to ensure the successful outreach, awareness, and utilization of the WILSON project's outcomes. This deliverable encompasses a series of key components that collectively contribute to the strategic communication and dissemination efforts throughout the project lifecycle: (1) Identification of WILSON stakeholders/profiling; (2) Dissemination methods, channels, associated activities and tools to reach expected impacts; (3) Dissemination procedures; (4) DEC activities' schedule and complementarities among partners. Report on the progress of the DEC activities during the project (M4, M18, M36) and final report (M48). This deliverable guides and evaluates the project's communication and dissemination efforts, fostering a dynamic and adaptive approach to maximize the long-term impact of the WILSON project.			

D16.3-17.2-18.2 Project synergies report	INTRACT	R, PU	M18, M36, M48
<p>1st, 2nd and final version of the report that serves as a comprehensive compilation of outcomes derived from the collaborative efforts and synergies established by the WILSON project with various European Union-funded projects, the Built4People partnership, and relevant platforms. These documents encapsulate the multifaceted engagements aimed at fostering a cohesive and interconnected ecosystem within the scientific and industrial community. The reports reveal WILSON's commitment to collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the establishment of a robust network that extends beyond project boundaries, contributing to the collective advancement of research and innovation in the European landscape.</p>			
D17.3-17.4-18.3 Knowledge management and IPR protection plan	INTRACT	R, SEN	M24, M18, M36
<p>1st, 2nd and final version of the plan that encapsulates the strategic framework and actionable insights formulated by WILSON to efficiently manage knowledge generated within the project and safeguard the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) associated with the final key exploitable results (KERs). This comprehensive plan, developed under the leadership of INTRACT and involving all project participants, encompasses various stages and methodologies to ensure a systematic and proactive approach. The plan serves as an essential tool for WILSON, ensuring the effective utilization of project outcomes while fostering a collaborative and legally secure environment among consortium members.</p>			

5.10.2. WP16-17-18 Milestones

Table 3 presents the milestones related to WP16-17-18 that will indicate the successful execution of the project.

Table 21 WP16-17-18 Milestones

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
2	WILSON initial documentation ready and project ready to start dissemination	INTRACT	M4	Project Handbook and DEC Plan approved by the PC and the GA. Website and first visual materials available.
4	Data spaces fully defined. Solutions developments' alpha version available Exploitation activities ready to start	TUE	M19	WP5, WP7, WP9 and WP11 checked and accepted. Architectures, models and algorithms initially developed and have been validated in a closed environment. Start of T17.2.
5	WILSON solutions start integration planning and preparation for large-scale demonstration. Initial	INTRACT	M25	Pilot partners start concrete conversations with developers for implementation (WPI3 starts). Initial agreements reached on exploitation routes for developed

No.	Description	Leader	Due date	Means of verification
	exploitation routes designed.			innovation (D17.4 checked and approved).
10	End of WILSON project	CIRCE	M48	All deliverables checked and approved WP leaders and the PC.

6. RISK ASSESSMENT

In the following table, a preliminary list of risks that may occur during WILSON implementation is shown, including the contingency plan for each potential risk. This section will be updated during the project execution with any additional risk that may be identified, or that occurs although it was unforeseen.

Table 22 WILSON Critical Risks

No.	Description	WP No.	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Closing the activity of one company or partner leaving the consortium	WPI-3	The consortium is highly qualified and would collectively assume tasks from a partner leaving the project. Otherwise, they would find within their large contact network the best partner for assuming the role lost.
2	Poor communication flow between partners	WPI-3	An open and dialectic approach will be applied in all the consortium meetings and correspondence and communication will be promoted and ensured by the project coordinator.
3	Lack of financial resources	WPI-3	Solvency of project partners has been assessed, ensuring their financial resources during the project execution. Most partners have already participated in national or EU projects, having wide experience and history, which reduces this risk.
4	Error in the estimation of the tasks' duration	WPI-3	Steering of the project will be frequent. Milestones and deliverables have been placed for control. Under delays detection PC will encourage a review of task procedure and partners to place extra effort.
5	Delay of one partner providing reports or activities	WPI-3	Estimation of tasks' duration has been made in agreement of all partners, so that, as a first approach, the DLVs and development should be given in time. In case of task delay which would suppose delay of others, adjustment on tasks' duration will be made to accomplish the time targets established and asking for additional effort to the partner responsible for the delay.
6	Problems between partners (IPR, internal disagreement, etc.)	WPI-3	Handbook (D1.1) will include all procedures already accepted in the CA. Democratic and dialectic approach will be applied in all consortium meetings and correspondence. IPR issues will be discussed and established in a common CA, signed by all partners.

No.	Description	WP No.	Proposed Mitigation Measures
7	Quality, scope and delay of partners work	WP1-3	Compulsory Work plan is established with operative plan to be prepared by WP leaders to avoid low quality, loss of direction or overloaded actions. If detected, PC will contact WP leader to revise. DLVs will always go through review process, including CIRCE.
8	Regulatory constraints for implementing a solution in a pilot site	WP14	Specific project solutions may be deployed in pilot or not depending on local legal and regulatory framework and therefore, recommendations based on experience and consultations will be provided and adapted to each local area.
9	Unavailability of data that would lead in inefficient optimization of models	WP4	WILSON includes experts with deep knowledge in their domains to ensure avoidance of assumptions or simplifications during modelling. Pilot partners are willing to install additional equipment for data gathering purposes to ensure that no lack of data appears during the course of the project.
10	Final construction of the Future Homes in UK pilot or the renovation project in the Italian pilot does not correspond with the planned timeline.	WP14	Construction of Future Homes is planned for 2025, while renovation project in Italy will occur within the project to implement the renovation tools. Enough time is planned from its scheduled finalisation until start of WP15. If delays happen, scope of demonstration will adapt to available capacity at the time, adapting the WP timeline if needed.
11	Limited access to pilot sites and delay in gathering information and running demos	WP4, WP14	Implementation of proactive measures with pilot partners to accelerate information collection and procurement processes to create a buffer of time that can be utilized in case of restrictions. Technical team always alert to speed up deployment. Alternative locations and actions (e.g., special permits) will be taken to ensure realisation of demo activities.
12	Failure to provide a concrete reference architecture specification	WP5-6, WP7-8	WILSON includes experienced experts in EU projects and systems development, who have already worked on and developed solutions for the data market. Also, WILSON will allow for a two-phase process for architecture specification for early problems detection.

No.	Description	WP No.	Proposed Mitigation Measures
13	Challenges implementing solutions at pilots or unexpected problems during operation	WP4, WP13, WP14	Initial effort will be placed during the first phase of the WP4 with a specific task (T4.1) to develop a comprehensive pilot analysis and deployment plan (refined in WP13), mitigating risks of later difficulties during implementation. Duration of pilot operation and monitoring tasks have been calculated considering possible complications and thus a contingent timeframe has been set.
14	Outputs not compliant with standards/reference architectures	WP14, WP15	Early tasks dedicated to data compliance (T4.4) and data spaces (T5.1) Partners, specially IDSA, are leaders in standards and IDS, minimizing this risk. Regular alignment will be ensured in tests. WP leader to monitor initiatives and emerging standards.
15	Interoperability problems between heterogeneous components / systems	WP4, WP9-10, WP11-12, WP13, WP14	To avoid problems on later stages, T4.4 will early analyse data compliance and requirements. This allows communication and alignment between partners to ensure data availability and interoperability. Partners will agree any decision that may impact interoperability
16	Deviations from the planned technical expectations	From WP4 to WP14	To align expectations, WP4 conducts an in-depth analysis of use cases and system functionalities with input from all partners, particularly developers and end users. Regular SC meetings and Exploitation sessions will discuss progress achieved in detail, achievements and expectations of the solutions developed to ensure alignment of required functionalities
17	Ineffective exploitation strategy and/or business models	WP16-18	WILSON counts with industrial and research partners with experience in developing, implementing and managing similar solutions, as well as business experts like RINA-C and INTRACT, and other entities with a large portfolio of clients and covering the entire value creation chain, which ensures enough expertise to modify and adapt exploitation if required.
18	Out of the radar competition could hinder exploitation of results	WP16-18	Market intelligence activities will ensure continuous monitoring of competition. Close interaction with relevant on-going R&I projects will reveal features that need to be included in

No.	Description	WP No.	Proposed Mitigation Measures
			the WILSON offering and alert the consortium for the acceleration of development and exploitation activities / WP leaders will ensure the quality of the relevant activities.
19	Poor dissemination to the stakeholders	WP16-18	Wide dissemination will be planned and updated to avoid this risk. All partners will use different channels to draw visitors to website: social media, newsletter, digital outlets, etc. In addition, it will be promoted at all events attended by consortium partners.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The Project Management Plan has clearly presented the roles and team involved in the project. At the same time, this document introduces a Work breakdown structure, with the objectives of the WPs, the relationship among them, the Gantt (overall and per WP) as well as a detailed breakdown of the tasks.

With this document, which will be updated in the future, all the partners have a useful tool that allows to understand better the project and, together with the D1.1 Project Handbook, will help the partners to proper develop and monitor the work expected during WILSON project lifetime.

wilson-project.eu

wilson-project

wilson-project

wilson_project_

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147267